

A Novel Extraction Procedure to Determine the Noise Parameters of On-Wafer Devices

Luciano Boglione
 Naval Research Laboratory
 4555 Overlook Avenue SW
 Washington, DC 20375

Abstract—A new procedure for the extraction of noise parameters of on-wafer devices is presented and validated experimentally for the first time. The procedure is based on the noise figure measurement of similar devices of different size and biased at constant drain current density J_{ds} and constant drain voltage V_{ds} . Key to its implementation is a scalable noise model. The model in use is the Pospieszalski noise model, based on the equivalent noise temperatures T_{gs} and T_{ds} of the gate-source and the drain-source resistance, respectively. The new procedure also outlines a path towards the experimental validation of all the noise temperatures associated with the device's lossy elements.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Pospieszalski noise model [1] has been demonstrated to provide a simple, yet robust approach to modeling the noise performance of microwave devices. The model is also scalable and it has been used for MMIC design [2]. The core model, shown in Fig. 1, consists of the gate-source impedance, the drain-source admittance and a complex voltage-controlled current source. The gate-source resistance R_{gs} and the drain-source resistance R_{ds} are also uncorrelated noise sources that fully describe the noise performance of the device. The available noise powers are described by the equivalent noise temperatures T_{gs} and T_{ds} , respectively. The gate-drain admittance introduces a feedback path that is not considered part of the core model.

Fig. 1 – The Pospieszalski noise model in use for the characterization of the FET transistor vs. device periphery P_d .

The Pospieszalski noise model has been validated over a number of technologies [3] and it has been verified that is

well suited for a scalable implementation [4] against both bias and size P_d . Good noise performance vs. experimental data is obtained by the model if the values of the core components are extracted with great care. Then, the evaluation of the equivalent temperatures T_{gs} and T_{ds} is often based on the use of a simulator matching the experimental data against the simulated performance. Guidelines for a meaningful determination of the equivalent noise temperatures have been offered [1], [5], [6], some [7] extending the mixed measurement-simulation approach to include the normalized equivalent temperature T_{gd} of the gate-drain feedback admittance.

This paper will introduce and validate for the first time a novel analytical approach [8] to the determination of the noise temperatures of the Pospieszalski model. The approach requires the measurement of the noise figure with a number of devices of varying peripheries. The minimum number of devices to be measured is set by the number of independent noise temperatures to be determined. No external tuners are required.

This paper's main goal is to introduce and validate the new technique. Supporting measurements from a number of on-wafer devices have been taken and will be included in the final paper submission.

II. CORE IDEA

The noise parameters are obtained by a least square approximation applied to the well known noise figure expression at a given frequency [9]:

$$F(Y_S) = F_{\min} + R_n \frac{|Y_S - Y_{S_{\text{opt}}}|^2}{G_S} \quad (1)$$

where F_{\min} , R_n and $Y_{S_{\text{opt}}}$ are a form of the noise parameters; and $Y_S = G_S + jB_S$ is the source impedance. Equation (1) is obtained from an equivalent expression that includes the noise correlation matrix [10]:

$$F(Y_S) = 1 + \frac{\mathbf{y}_S^+ \mathbf{C}_{\text{dev}}^T \mathbf{y}_S}{4N_i G_S} \quad (2a)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_S^+ = [Y_S \quad 1] \quad (2b)$$

where $\mathbf{C}_{\text{dev}}^T$ is the correlation matrix of the device in transmission representation; $+$ is the hermitian conjugate operation; $N_i = kT_o B$ is the noise power in a bandwidth B ; T_o is the standard noise temperature (290 [K]); and \mathbf{y}_S is a 2×1 source vector that includes the source impedance Y_S .

Expression (2) shows the basis of the standard extraction of noise parameters: an external tuner allows the noise parameters within the correlation matrix to be determined by measuring the noise figure over a number of known vector values \mathbf{y}_S . However, the same expression (2) also suggests a new procedure tailored to on-wafer devices: since the Pospieszalski's core noise model shown in Fig. 1 is scalable with size P_d , the noise correlation matrix is a function of the device size and the collection of $(P_d; F)$ pairs allows the determination of the noise parameters similarly to the standard noise parameter extraction based on the $(Y_S; F)$ pairs.

Although the core idea may not be a general measurement procedure (e.g. one device is not sufficient for this procedure to be executed successfully), noise parameters are of greatest value when obtained for on-wafer devices. Further, an external tuner is no longer required as long as a number of similar devices of different size are available – a valuable simplification in both measurement setup and related costs. Finally, the selection of $Y_S = 1/(50 \Omega)$ is natural for the new procedure and corresponds to a standard 50Ω noise figure measurement.

III. OUTLINE OF THE PROCEDURE

The following formalism is adopted: a hat on a lower case letter is used to indicate a component normalized to the device periphery (e.g. \hat{y}_{gs} [S/mm] or \hat{r}_{ds} [$\Omega \cdot \text{mm}$]); upper case letters indicate a standard component (e.g. Y_{gs} [S] or R_{ds} [Ω]).

The novel measurement procedure starts with an accurate extraction of the component values of the small signal model, shown in Fig. 1. Parasitic components such as pad admittance $Y_{\text{pad}} = G_{\text{pad}} + j\omega C_{\text{pad}}$ and access line impedance $Z_{\text{acc}} = R_{\text{acc}} + j\omega L_{\text{acc}}$ model the on-wafer embedding structures. Additional parasitics such as the series impedance $Z_{\text{src}} = R_{\text{src}} + j\omega L_{\text{src}}$ are easily handled.

The Pospieszalski noise model relies on two uncorrelated noise sources T_{gs} and T_{ds} associated with \hat{r}_{gs} and \hat{r}_{ds} . The noisy gate-drain admittance

$$\left(\frac{1}{\hat{y}_{gd}}\right)^{-1} = \hat{r}_{gd} + \frac{1}{j\omega \hat{c}_{gd}} \quad [\Omega \cdot \text{mm}] \quad (3)$$

may be assumed at ambient (reference) temperature T_o [7]. All losses in the setup are assumed to be at temperature T_o .

The available noise power associated with either \hat{r}_{gs} , \hat{r}_{ds} or \hat{r}_{gd} is independent of the resistance value – i.e. of the resistor's size P_d – but their Thevenin equivalent noise voltage source $|v_x|^2$ is not:

$$kT_x B = N_i t_x \quad (4)$$

$$|v_x|^2 = 4N_i t_x \left(\frac{\hat{r}_x}{P_d}\right) \quad (5)$$

where $N_i = kT_o B$, $t_x = T_x/T_o$ and $x = \text{gs}, \text{ds}$ or gd .

The new procedure is based on the execution of the following steps:

- 1) Determine the parasitic elements associated with the on-wafer embedding structures (pad admittance Y_{pad} , input and output access line impedances $Z_{\text{acc},i} = Z_{\text{acc},o} = Z_{\text{acc}} = R_{\text{acc}} + j\omega L_{\text{acc}}$);

- 2) For each device of periphery P_d and biased at constant drain current density J_{ds} and drain-source voltage V_{ds} ,
 - a) Measure the scattering parameters;
 - b) Measure the noise figure F_{50} associated with a source admittance $Y_S = (1/50)$ [S];
- 3) Determine the core model components \hat{r}_{gs} , \hat{r}_{ds} , \hat{r}_{gd} [$\Omega \cdot \text{mm}$]; \hat{c}_{gs} , \hat{c}_{ds} , \hat{c}_{gd} [pF/mm]; $|\hat{g}_m| = G_m$ [mS/mm]; and $\angle \hat{g}_m = -\omega\tau$ [rad];
- 4) De-embed the noise contributions of the parasitic components from the measured F_{50} ; and
- 5) Calculate the equivalent noise temperatures T_{gs} and T_{ds} associated with \hat{r}_{gs} and \hat{r}_{ds} respectively.

The execution of steps #1 and #2a yields the required information to execute step #3. Step #2b allows step #4 and #5 to be implemented as follows.

The core components can be used to describe the device in terms of hybrid matrix with uncorrelated noise sources:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_1 \\ I_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\hat{y}_{gs} P_d} & 0 \\ -j\Omega & \hat{y}_{ds} P_d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ V_2 \end{bmatrix} + n_{\text{core}}^H \quad (6a)$$

$$n_{\text{core}}^H n_{\text{core}}^H + = 4N_i \begin{bmatrix} \hat{r}_{gs} \frac{P_d}{P_d} & 0 \\ 0 & t_{ds} \frac{P_d}{\hat{r}_{ds}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6b)$$

where $+$ is the hermitian conjugate operation and

$$\left(\frac{1}{\hat{y}_{gs}}\right)^{-1} = \hat{r}_{gs} + \frac{1}{j\omega \hat{c}_{gs}} \quad [\Omega \cdot \text{mm}] \quad (7a)$$

$$\hat{y}_{ds} = \frac{1}{\hat{r}_{ds}} + j\omega \hat{c}_{ds} \quad [\text{mS/mm}] \quad (7b)$$

$$\omega_t = \frac{\hat{g}_m}{\hat{c}_{gs}} \quad [\text{rad/s}] \quad (7c)$$

$$\Omega = \frac{\omega_t}{\omega} \quad [-]. \quad (7d)$$

The constant ω_t is independent of size and formally a complex number because $\hat{g}_m = G_m \cdot \exp(-j\omega\tau)$. If $\omega\tau \ll 1$, $\hat{g}_m \approx G_m$.

Since linearity is assumed, the noise vector n_{core}^H in (6) can be transformed into the noise vector n_{core}^Y in Y representation by a proper linear transformation; then, the gate-drain admittance (3) can be added to both signal matrix and noise vector to obtain:

$$n_{\text{fet}}^Y n_{\text{fet}}^{Y+} = 4N_i (C_{gs}^Y t_{gs} + C_{ds}^Y t_{ds} + C_{gd}^Y t_{gd}) \quad (8)$$

where

$$C_{gs}^Y(\omega; P_d) = |\hat{r}_{gs} \hat{y}_{gs}|^2 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & j\Omega^* \\ -j\Omega & |\Omega|^2 \end{bmatrix} \frac{P_d}{\hat{r}_{gs}} \quad (9a)$$

$$C_{ds}^Y(\omega; P_d) = \Re\{\hat{r}_{ds} \hat{y}_{ds}\} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \frac{P_d}{\hat{r}_{ds}} \quad (9b)$$

$$C_{gd}^Y(\omega; P_d) = \Re\{\hat{r}_{gd} \hat{y}_{gd}\} \begin{bmatrix} +1 & -1 \\ -1 & +1 \end{bmatrix} \frac{P_d}{\hat{r}_{gd}} \quad (9c)$$

Expressions (9) highlight the dependance of the correlation matrix $C_{\text{fet}}^Y = n_{\text{fet}}^Y n_{\text{fet}}^{Y+}$ (8) on the device periphery P_d as expected. Further, (8) can be described as linearly dependent on the normalized equivalent noise temperatures t_{gs} , t_{ds} and t_{gd} .

Careful transformations allow the correlation matrix $\mathbf{C}_{\text{meas}}^T$ measured at the probe tips to be referred to the internal nodes of the device. Eventually,

$$\frac{(F_n - 1) G_S}{P_{d_n}} = A_n t_{ds} + B_n t_{gs} + C_n t_{gd} \quad (10)$$

is obtained with (2) for each device with known periphery P_{d_n} . The subscript n in (10) refers to the measurement of the n^{th} device with known size P_{d_n} . The term F_n is the noise figure F_{50} de-embedded to the device terminals. The coefficients A_n , B_n and C_n stem from (9) and (2), to which they are linearly related but may not be linear functions of the device size because of the transformation from T to Y representation that links (8) to (2). Expression (10) requires a minimum of $n = 2$ independent measurement to calculate the unknowns t_{gs} and t_{ds} at a given angular frequency ω . If more than 2 device sizes are measured, (10) is over-determined and a least square method can be implemented. Note that the procedure can be easily expanded to include the experimental determination of t_{gd} .

Fig. 2 – Measurements (dotted, blue trace) vs. simulation (solid, red trace) of the FETs’ scattering parameter magnitudes based on Fig. 1’s model. The data in the plots is referred to the probe tips plane and include the embedding parasitics.

IV. VALIDATION

The procedure was demonstrated theoretically in [8] and is demonstrated here with measured data. Scattering parameters are collected for $n = 6$ FET devices of different size from which the core component values are determined. Two devices have same periphery P_d but different number of fingers and finger widths. Noise figure and scattering parameter data has been measured on-wafer up to 15 [GHz] at $J_{ds} \approx 125$ [mA/mm] and $V_{ds} = 6$ [V]. Pad capacitance ($C_{pad} \approx 23.943$ [fF]) and access line inductance ($L_{acc} \approx 62.787$ [pH]) have been extracted from available on-wafer de-embedding structures. Negligible loss associated with (a) the pad elements C_{pad} and L_{acc} ; (b) the device source impedance Z_{src} ; and (c) the device finger loss have been found negligible experimentally. The transition frequency $f_t = |\omega_t|/(2\pi)$ is approximately 51 [GHz] at the given bias point. The condition

$\omega\tau \ll 1$ is verified ($\omega\tau \approx 7.60$ [deg] at 15 [GHz]). Measured scattering parameters are compared with the simulated scattering parameters after extracting the component values of Fig. 1 and good agreement is found as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3 – Plots of the simulated (blue), approximated (black) and measured (red) noise figure F_{50} (top left) and the ratio (11) over frequency (bottom left) and corresponding quantities over size (right) at 10 [GHz].

Scripts implementing the novel extraction procedure of Section III have been written in order to calculate Pospieszalski’s noise temperatures: $T_{gs} \approx 231.98$ [K] and $T_{ds} \approx 4591.13$ [K] are obtained. The calculations are applied on a smoothed dataset of the measured noise figure identified by the subscript apx (approximated). The ratio

$$\hat{y} \triangleq \frac{(F_{50} - 1) \Re\{Y_S\}}{P_d} \begin{bmatrix} S \\ m \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

defined in (10) and calculated at the probe tips planes is plotted in Fig. 3 vs. frequency and device size at 10 [GHz] and it is compared with the corresponding simulated results. The ratio (11) is of particular interest since it untangles the overlapping noise figure traces – compare F_{50} from (2) and \hat{y} from (11) in Fig. 3. The noise parameters satisfy the fundamental constraint $4NT_o/T_{min} \geq 1$ of the noise correlation matrix by construction.

Some numerical sensitivity of T_{gs} and T_{ds} values has been observed. The author believes that a more sophisticated scalable model of the device may reduce this sensitivity. Also, enhancing the numerical calculations may provide a tangible improvement. Finally, the technique relies on associating noise sources with noise temperatures that are independent of frequency and size as in the Pospieszalski model. On-wafer FETs constitute a broad set of devices which this procedure is perfectly tailored for.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has outlined and validated a novel procedure that allows the determination of the noise parameters based on the Pospieszalski noise model. The procedure is suited for on-wafer determination of the noise parameters since it relies on devices of different size rather than on the use of external tuners. The new procedure requires that the devices

be biased at the same drain current density J_{ds} and drain-source voltage V_{ds} , and that the number of available device sizes equals the number of equivalent noise temperatures to be determined. Consequently, the procedure opens up the experimental possibility of determining the noise temperatures of all scalable lossy elements of a noise model, and potentially of all noise sources in the experimental setup. A patent application to protect the novel extraction procedure has also been filed in September 2012 [11].

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the United States Office of Naval Research. The author is also grateful to Dr. Harvey Newman for making measurement equipment available for device testing.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. W. Pospieszalski, "Modelling of noise parameters of MESFET's and MODFET's and their frequency and temperature dependence," *IEEE Trans. on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 37, No. 9, pp. 1340–1350, September 1989.
- [2] B. Hughes, J. Perdomo, and H. Kondoh, "12 GHz low-noise MMIC amplifier designed with a noise model that scales with MODFET size and bias," *IEEE Trans. on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 41, No. 12, pp. 2311–2316, December 1993.
- [3] M. W. Pospieszalski, "Interpreting transistor noise," *Microwave Magazine, IEEE*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 61–69, Oct. 2010.
- [4] B. Hughes, "A temperature noise model for extrinsic FET's," *IEEE Trans. on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 40, No. 9, pp. 1821–1831, September 1992.
- [5] G. Dambrine, H. Cappy, F. Danneville, and A. Cappy, "A new method for on wafer noise measurement," *IEEE Trans. on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 41, No. 3, pp. 375–381, March 1993.
- [6] P. J. Tasker, W. Reinert, B. Hughes, J. Braunstein, and M. Schlechtweg, "Transistor noise parameter extraction using a 50 ohm measurement system," *IEEE MTT-S International Microwave Symposium Digest*, pp. 1251–1254, Atlanta, 1993.
- [7] T. Felgentreff, G. Olbrich, and P. Russer, "Noise parameter modeling of HEMTs with resistor temperature noise sources," in *Microwave Symposium Digest, 1994., IEEE MTT-S International*, vol. 2, May 1994, pp. 853–856.
- [8] L. Bogleione, "A noise parameters extraction procedure suitable for on-wafer device characterization," *2012 IEEE International Semiconductor Conference Dresden-Grenoble (ISCDG)*, Grenoble, France, September 24–26, 2012.
- [9] R. Q. Lane, "The determination of device noise parameters," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 57, pp. 1461–1462, August 1969.
- [10] H. Hillbrand and P. H. Russer, "An efficient method for computer aided noise analysis of linear amplifier networks," *IEEE Trans. on Circuits and Systems*, vol. CAS–23, No. 4, pp. 235–238, April 1976.
- [11] L. Bogleione, "A noise parameters extraction procedure for on-wafer device characterization," Provisional Patent 61/703,384, Sept. 20, 2012.